

Srinivas University

College of Social Science and Humanities

From,

Dr. Laveena D'Mello
Dean,
College of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Srinivas University, City Campus,
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.

To,

Dr. Meena Montheiro,
Dean, Research Council,
School of Social Work,
Roshni Nilaya, Mangaluru- 575001.

Sub: To participate in BOS meeting of CSSH.

Greetings from College of Social Sciences and Humanities!

We would like to request you to participate in our Board of Studies meeting which will be conducted on **March 8th Monday 2021 at 10.30 am** at room no 6, at College of Social Sciences, Srinivas University. Kindly find the attached agenda below.

Agenda

1. To approve the MSW Syllabus with changes made for the academic year 2021.
2. To Approve the new Course
3. Identifying the subjects.
4. Value added courses
5. The syllabus
6. Rules and regulation
7. Academic calendar and exams
8. Internal and External Paper setters
9. Valuation
10. Any other matter

Your participation will be highly appreciable.

Thanking you.

Yours Sincerely,

08/03/2021

Dr. Laveena D'Mello

DEAN

Institute of Social Science & Humanities
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

Srinivas University

College of Social Science and Humanities

From,

Dr. Laveena D'Mello
Dean,
College of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Srinivas University, City Campus,
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.

To,

Dr. Swetha K.T.
Director, Anirveda, Pump well
Mangaluru- 575002.

Sub: To participate in BOS meeting of CSSH.

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Yours Sincerely,

08/03/2021
Dr. Laveena D'Mello

Srinivas University
College of Social Science and Humanities

From,

Dr. Laveena D'Mello
Dean, College of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Srinivas University, City Campus,
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.

To,

Dr. Vidya
Assistant Professor,
College of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Srinivas University, City Campus,
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.

Sub: To participate in BOS meeting of CSSH.

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Yours Sincerely,

Dr. Laveena D'Mello *08/03/2021*

DEAN

Srinivas University
College of Social Science and Humanities

From,

Dr. Laveena D'Mello
Dean, College of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Srinivas University, City Campus,
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.

To,

Prof. Pradeep M.D.
Assistant Professor,
College of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Srinivas University, City Campus,
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.

Sub: To participate in BOS meeting of CSSH.

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Yours Sincerely,

Dr. Laveena D'Mello

DEAN

Srinivas University
College of Social Science and Humanities

From,

Dr. Laveena D'Mello
Dean, College of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Srinivas University, City Campus,
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.

To,

Mr. Gururaj
Research Scholar
College of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Srinivas University, City Campus,
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.

Sub: To participate in BOS meeting of CSSH.

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Your participation will be highly appreciable.

Thanking you.

Yours Sincerely,

 08/03/2021

Dr. Laveena D'Mello

DEAN

Srinivas University

College of Social Science and Humanities

The report of the Board of Studies of BSW course was conducted on **March 8th Monday 2021 at 10.30 am** at room no 6, at College of Social Sciences, Srinivas University.

The following members were present for the meeting

1. Dr. Laveena D'Mello
2. Mr. Pradeep M.D.
3. Dr. Vidaya
4. Mr. Gururaj
5. Dr. Meena Monthiero
6. Dr. Shwetha K.T.

During the meeting the introduction of the course was done by the dean of the college Dr. Laveena D'Mello for the committee. And many issues related to new syllabus was discussed. The following resolutions were taken.

1. **To approve the MSW Syllabus with changes made for the academic year 2021:** There were changes made in the syllabus by changing the units and topics inside the subjects. Course objectives modified and course outcome and pedagogy were added in the syllabus. Committee members were provided the syllabus well in advance to go through before the meeting. And same was briefed during the meeting. Minor modifications were made and same have been approved in the meeting.

Resolution: The changes which are made in the content of the syllabus were highlighted and same have been approved in the meeting. Also, the course objectives, course outcome, and Pedagogy have been approved in the meeting.

2. **To approve the new Course:** First and foremost, the new course was approved. Since we have MSW PG course wanted to introduce UG this year with all the members approved the same.

Resolution: Resolution taken and permission granted in the BOS committee.

3. **Identifying the subjects:** The subjects were introduced and same was discussed and approved

Course Structure : SEMESTER 1			SEMESTER 2		
SN	Subject	Mks	S N	Subject	Mks
1	Fundamentals of Communication	100	1	Business Communication	100
2	Introduction to social work	100	2	Scope of social work	100

3	Social Science perspective for social work	100	3	Work with Individuals and Family	100
4	Economic Concepts of Social Work	100	4	Human Growth and Development	100
5	Indian Constitution & Environmental Studies	100	5	Indian Legal System	100
6	Social Work Practicum-I	100	6	Social Work Practicum-II	100
7	Communication Skill Assessment Programme	50	7	Skill Assessment and language proficiency	50
8	Seminar and Group presentation	50	8	Seminar and Group presentation	50
		700			700
SEMESTER 3			SEMESTER 4		
1	Social Intervention with groups and individuals	100	1	Work with communities	100
2	Social Problems in India	100	2	Social Case Work	100
3	Introduction to Family Education	100	3	Management of developmental and welfare services	100
4	Introduction to Rural, Urban and Tribal communities	100	4	Social Welfare Administration	100
5	Organizational Behaviour	100	5	Stress Management	100
6	Social Work Practicum-III	100	6	Social Work Practicum-IV	100
7	Employability Skills Programme	50	7	Fundamentals of Computer Skills	50
8	Seminar and Group presentation	50	8	Seminar and Group presentation	50
		700			700
SEMESTER 5			SEMESTER 6		
1	Social Movements and Social Action	100	1	Social Policy and Planning	100
2	Social Work Research	100	2	Child Protection and child rights	100
3	Human Growth & Development	100	3	Community Development	100
4	Women Empowerment	100	4	Social Change and Development	100
5	Social Work and Health care	100	5	Social Work Practicum-VI	100
6	Social Policy, Planning, and Development	100	6	Project Work (Field)	200
7	Social Work Practicum-V	100			
		700			700

Resolution: Resolution taken and subjects semester wise approved.

4. **Value added courses:** Regarding value added courses were added in the syllabus. Same were discussed.

Resolution: Resolution taken by adding value added courses in the syllabus and permission granted in the BOS committee.

5. **The syllabus:** Syllabus was disused orally. And it was suggested to do some changes in the individual subject unites. Same was noted down and will be done correction.

Resolution: Resolution was taken and syllabus was approved.

6. **Rules and regulation :** Rules and regulation and examination, credit system everything was discussed and finalized

Resolution: Resolution taken and rules and regulations were finalized in permission granted in the BOS committee.

7. **Academic calendar and exams:** Academic calendar was proposed. But not finalized due to the examination of the lower classes and due to corona. The uncertainty of the classes it was not finalized, but discussion done on this.

8. **Internal and External Paper setters:** The list of the internal and external paper setters were identified and same was put-up in the meetings. The additional external members were added and the list was finalized.

Resolution: Resolution taken on the examiner internal and external paper setters and final list of the BOE committee members was approved. During the meeting. The members are as following members.

B.S.W. Programme

Board of Studies (BOE) – 2021

Sl. No.	Name	Designation	Qualification	Status
1	Dr. Laveena D'Mello	Assistant Professor	B.A., M.S.W., M.Phil, Ph.D. 17 years teaching experience	Chair person
2	Mr. Pradeep M.D.	Assistant Professor	M.S.W., M.A., L.L.B., L.L.M., PGDM	Member

			(Ph.D. doing) 11 years teaching experience	
3	Dr. Vidya	Part Time	M.S.W., Ph.D. 06 years teaching experience	Member
4	Mr. Gururaj	Part - time	M.S.W.,(Ph.D.) 4 years teaching experience	Member
6	Dr. Meena Monthiero	External	M.S.W., Ph.D. 19 years teaching experience	External Member
7.	Indu Nair	Part time	M.S.W. M.S.W.,(Ph.D.) 6 years teaching experience	Member
8.	Anusuya Kamath	External	M.S.W.,(Ph.D.) 10 years teaching experience	External Member
9.	Anuradha Shetty	External	M.S.W., (Ph.D.) 11 years teaching experience	External Member
10.	Veena B.K	External	M.S.W., (Ph.D.) 10 years teaching experience	External Member

9. **Valuation:** Valuation process was also discussed during the meeting. The two separate valuation done at university and if there is variation in the marks the maximum marks can be considered. Review is also done. And if there is more than 20% difference then the third valuation is considered. And all these process is done by the controller of evaluation and his direction.

Any other matter: After the general discussion about the admissions and the process of admission, and it is challenging to get students for the course it may be difficult but not impossible. All have to work in hand in hand, so that the course can be conducted successfully. The meeting was ended at 3.00 pm with formal vote of thanks by the chair person Dr. Laveena D.Mello.

Date: 08/03/2021

Place: Mangalore

Laveena D. Mello
08/03/2021
DEAN

Srinivas University

College of Social Science and Humanities

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